

A GOOD COACH

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Annotation

Extracurricular activities have many **advantages** like increase in sociability, learning new things and better motivation for school. Pupils become more and more fond of English if they are involved in extracurricular activities. And not only that, but they also improve their pronunciation, vocabulary, communicative skills as well. It's true, there are English lessons which use songs and games and short role plays but we cannot use them all the time, we have to teach grammar, to have pupils practise it through worksheets, we also have to teach reading and writing. Well it's a fun way to learn and practice English on the one hand ,but on the other hand it allows students to communicate with and understand others in new ways.

Key words: Extracurricular activities, sociability, pronunciation, worksheets. Students who have participated in Dramatic activities are less likely to have difficulty speaking in public, will be better able to put themselves into others' shoes and relate to them, and will have a more positive, confident self image. Participation in Dramatic activity requires self control and discipline that will serve the student well in all aspects of life. Students in Drama will learn to work together, to cooperate and to find the best way for each member of a group to contribute. How does a Drama lesson "work"? Well, students start with some warm up activities such as "Mirrors" or tongue twisters (great for voice techniques, rhythm, pronunciation). Mirroring is a way of developing concentration skills and it goes on like this: everyone takes a partner. (If there is an odd number, the teacher pairs with someone.) To have your activity well done it is necessary for a teacher to be a **GOOD COACH**. What is it?

Before we discuss what qualities and skill sets that make for a good coach, we need to first acknowledge how very difficult this profession of coaching really is. Coaching is sometimes a thankless, frustrating "no-win" kind of job. It's an occupation that is most often done in a public fishbowl. In other words, if you coach, then you are in a highly visible position that continually exposes you to the public's scrutiny and evaluation. It's one of those professions where the

general public regularly weighs in on what kind of a job they think you're doing whether you want their evaluation or not.

When it comes to judging your job performance, everyone seems to be an expert and have the "qualifications" to criticize you. Fans, parents, students, alumni, the media, and the team's organization or administration all seem at the ready to offer you either the thumbs up or thumbs down signal. What's even more frustrating for a coach is that so much of this external judgment comes from individuals who don't seem to have a clue about you, your players, or what you're trying to accomplish with the team.

Coaching is also one of those jobs where your professional effectiveness is almost always narrowly measured by something that is very often totally out of your control: winning and losing.

In many ways you can be a bad or ineffective coach, yet because you are lucky enough to have great players on your squad, you win all the time. Because of this external record you are considered in your profession to be a "great" coach. Similarly, you can be a wonderful coach and teacher but because of a lack of player talent, luck, or other circumstances beyond your control such as player injuries, your won-loss record is just mediocre and, as a consequence of this, you're seen as an ineffective coach.

Not sure how you should use this list of extracurriculars? Just follow the six steps outlined in this section, and you'll be on your way to choosing the best extracurricular for you!

Step 1: Brainstorm Extracurricular Ideas

What are your interests? Have you always wanted to try out something related to art, but weren't sure if it would be worth your time, or if it would be viewed favorably by a college admissions team? Keep in mind that colleges don't really care about *what* kind of activity you are doing - instead, they want to see that **you are doing something that you are passionate about**. So make a list of all of your interests - both things that you are already interested in and other areas that intrigue you and you'd like to learn more about.

Step 2: See Which Extracurriculars Fit Your Interests

Look through the list below and see if any of the activities match your interests. You may see some ways that you hadn't thought of before to pursue an interest! Keep in mind that there can be a lot of different outlets for each interest you have. For example, if you want to play an instrument, you can take private classes, play in your school's marching band, play in a community concert band, or work as part of the orchestra for your school's next musical.

Step 3: Research Different Extracurricular Options

Research to see if these activities are available at your high school or in your community. If there is something you are very passionate about that's not already offered, consider starting up a group of your own. But if you aren't sure that the interest will stick and you only want to try it out, it's probably best to find a different outlet for your curiosity.

Step 4: Join Some Activities

The next step is to **start doing activities!** But how many should you do? If you are a freshman, I would recommend trying out a bunch of different activities--up to ten if there are that many you have an interest in. The idea at this stage is to **sample a variety of extracurriculars.** Once you start to get an idea of which activities are going to really help you develop the interests you are most passionate about, you can dedicate more time to those and drop the others.

Step 5: Narrow Down Your Extracurriculars

If you are a sophomore, junior, or senior, you should hopefully already have an idea of the kinds of activities that you want to focus on. **Make a list of the top five activities that interest you.** If you have the time to try out all five, go for it. This will give you a bit of time to experiment and see what's most of interest. If you don't have time, try to narrow down your top five to three activities.

Step 6: Increase Your Impact in a Few Activities

Remember to not spread yourself too thin, especially if you are above freshman year. It's more important to spend significant time in each activity than it is to have a long list of activities. **Choose activities that will allow you to make a meaningful impact, either in your own development, or in the community.**

1. S _ F _	2. _ H _ _ F	3. A _ M C _ A _ R	4. M _ _ R O _	5. _ R A _ E _ S
6. F _ R E _ L _ C E	7. T _ B L _	8. C O _ K _ _	9. B O _ K C _ S _	10. _ A T _
11. W _ R D _ _ B _	12. C _ A _ _	13. F _ _ D _ E	14. _ E _	15. C _ O _ _
 <small>clipart.com/51311</small>				
16. D _ S _	17. L _ _ P	18. T _ L E _ _ S I _ N	19. T V S _ A _ D	20. S _ _ K

Here re some examples of activities that the teacher can use for after curricular activities:

Furniture in my house.

This activity helps to create critical thinking and organize pupils to arrange furniture in their homes. For good results of this activity you have to:

1. Make two copies of each handout
2. Cut one copy into pieces
3. Ask pupils to write in the missing letters
4. Ask pupils to arrange pictures in order (by names of rooms)

There is another funny activity nabbed as “So Silly”. This activity helps pupils to understand colors and words.

ACTIVITY

1. As a class, review the following parts of speech:

noun – a word that names a person, place, or thing (*chair, friend, paper*)

verb – an action word (*jumped, pushed, read*)

adjective – a word that describes something or somebody (*little, soft, happy*)

2. Arrange for the students to work in pairs.
3. Distribute Activity Sheets A and B. Have the students color the word balloons according to the directions on the activity sheet (nouns red, verbs blue, adjectives yellow). Help student pairs check their work and discard cards colored incorrectly. Or, if you prefer, provide fresh activity sheets so that students can make corrections.
4. Then have students cut the cards apart on the dashed lines.
5. Explain that most sentences are built according to familiar patterns. The simplest sentences are built with a single noun and a single verb:
Dogs barked.
Children giggled.
6. Have the student pairs build similar sentences by combining various red cards (nouns) and blue cards (verbs). **Note:** These short sentences may sound choppy without the addition of articles (*a, an, the*).
7. Distribute Activity Sheet C.
8. Explain that students will build silly sentences according to a common sentence pattern that is more complex than the noun/verb pattern. Instruct the student pairs to randomly select cards of the correct colors and place them in the labeled rectangles. Student pairs can take turns reading the resulting silly sentences to each other.
9. Finally, distribute Activity Sheet D (1 per student), and have each student copy a favorite silly sentence and illustrate it. Display the completed activity sheets where classmates can read them.

Finally there are countless benefits to engaging in extra-curricular activities outside of school. Exploring diverse interests helps students better understand themselves and discover new opportunities in life. They become better equipped to handle unexpected occurrences and develop the skills to be prepared for anything life throws their way. In addition to the myriad of benefits extra-curricular activities offer, they look great on school and job applications. It is a small step towards ensuring our children's success, but one worth taking. In the end, we want our students to be well-rounded individuals, and extra-curricular activities are ideal for accomplishing that.

Resources

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